
**A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS OF MAJOR TOURIST ATTRACTION IN PARNER TEHSIL,
AHMEDNAGAR DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA**

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ABSTRACT:

Tourism is one of the largest and fastest growing sector in world. These tourism sector providing largest employment. Tourism sector has play a major role in development process. Nowadays, India is having greater scope in tourism sector. This study is aimed to introduce exact situation and importance of many wonderful, useful distinctive places in Parner tehsil and emphasized the various geographical and religious aspects of developmental issues of the area. Parner tehsil is enriched of geographical, historical, and cultural tourism aspects.

The object of study region is, to highlight the attractive tourist destinations and religious places in the region. This study based on primary and secondary data. Tourist attractions in the district as is, natural beauty, potholes, caves, temples, ideal village, industries, festivals etc. To the visit of tourist, which requires natural resources, infrastructural and transportation facilities, accommodation, food, recreation, sightseeing, shopping and variety of facilities and services for use and enjoyments. The source of tourism depends on all these facilities.

Keyword: *Geographical Analysis, Tourism, Tourist Centers, natural resources*

INTRODUCTION:

Parner tehsil is important tehsil in Ahmednagar district. The natural resources, caves, potholes, plateau, hill ranges, scenery, ideal village, agricultural and industrial development are very important resources of tourist attraction. The various natural and cultural features in Parner tehsil.

STUDY REGION:

The Parner taluka lies in Ahmednagar district consists of 131 villages and one urban centre. Geographically extension of taluka between 18°49'40'' N to 19° 21'13'' N Latitude and 74° 10' 22''E to 74° 38' 34'' E Longitude. Geographically, it located on Deccan plateau. The region is drained by river Kukadi, Ghod & Sina. Sangamner tehsil lies in northwest, Rahuri tehsil lies in northeast, Nagar tehsil lies in east, Shrigonda tehsil lies in southern side & Pune districts boundary belongs to western side of Parner tehsil. The geographical area of the study region is 1930.28 sq. km and has population 274167 according to 2011 census. Out of the total population 140267 are male and 133900 are female population and the density of the population is 142 per sq. Km. Parner tehsil lies in the rain shadow or rain fed zone of Maharashtra state. National highway, state highway, major district road, other district road and village road are major routes of transport in Parner tehsil.

Study Region Location

LOCATION MAP OF PARNER TAHSIL

PARNER TAHSIL VILLAGE MAP

OBJECTIVES:

The main objectives of the study were as follows:

- 1) To study the profile of Parner tehsil
- 2) To highlight tourist places in study region
- 3) To review the progress of tourism related works in the study region.
- 4) To study the new employment opportunities through tourism industry in Parner tehsil

HYPOTHESIS:

Tourist can generate employment opportunities especially in the Parner tehsil.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research work is based on the primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected from visits to the various tourist centers with help of photographs, interviews and questionnaire of tourist, pilgrims, stakeholders etc.

Secondary data was collected from reference books, periodicals, booklets, daily newspapers, magazines, reports, internet etc.

TOURIST ATTRACTIONS IN THE PARNER TEHASIL:

Major tourist centers in the Parner tehsil are explained as follows-

Nighoj Potholes:

The archeological Gangetic potholes were present near Nighoj village. These potholes in local language called as Kund or Ranjankhalge. Nighoj potholes of river Kukadi a basalt rocky channel are supposed to be the biggest in Asia continent. Nighoj pothole recorded in Gunnies book of world record. These potholes 90 km away from Pune district centre and 30 km away from Pune-Ahmednagar road. Nighoj potholes is rocky stretch of 1.5 km which forms a boundary between Pune and Ahmednagar district. These potholes are formed by basalt rock of Kukadi river. The pothole length is two to three kilometer, width is ten meter and depth is twenty-five to fifty meter. Local peoples name it as 'Kund'. Near the river basin temple of Goddess Malganga is situated. Both bank of kukadi river devotee people built a temples. The annually festival of goddess Malganga is celebrated in month of March or April. Many pilgrims visited in festival to pothole. School-college students, researchers, stakeholders visited in whole year.

Padali Darya:

In Parner tehsil area having the famous geological variations. The famous geological attraction is stalactite and stalagmite in the caves of Padali Darya. Padali Darya located in Parner tehsil thirty-five kilometer away from north west side of parner city. Work of ground water in calcium carbonate cave. Development of stalactites, stalagmites and calcium depositions on the cave walls.

Stalactite are formed naturally after a longer process and the structures of calcium carbonate dolomite depositions. Stalactite segregate like straw and finally take shape of hard pillar.

Stalagmite is formed due to continuous percolation of saline water from limestone at floor of caves. Both stalactites and stalagmites length increasing year by year. During a period of one year 0.13 millimeter growth rates of these features. Padali darya cave, stalactites, stalagmites, animals and plants of these areas attraction of tourists.

Ralegan Siddhi:

Ralegan Siddhi is famous for ideal village and well-known personality of Padmasri Anna Hajare. Under the guidance of Padmasri Anna Hajare villagers developed these village. Now a days this village play a role model of ideal village. Management and conservation of water, forest, soil, animal etc. attraction of visitors. Different projects and programs was organized in village. Rural development training center famous in India. All over India and out of Indian peoples are visit to Ralegan Siddhi.

Pimpalgaon Rotha:

Pimpalgaon Rotha famous for God Khandoba temple. Yearly five days festival Yatra is celebrated in the month of March. In every yatra five to seven lakh devotees visited pimpalgaon Rotha.

Supa MIDC and Windmill project:

Supa village and its surrounding area famous for industry and windmill. In Supa MIDC situated small and large scale industries. Near supa village on the hilly region established more than fifty windmills. This project run by Suzlon India ltd.

Dhokeshwar Cave:

Historical Dhokeshwar cave located in Dhoke village. This cave are curved during carvation period of Ajanta and Ellora caves. This site has religious importance because holy temple of lord Shiva is located. Thousands of people visit to this place in a year with religious and architectural aspects.

Also in Parner tehsil Pimpalner, Valavane, Jamgaon, Kanhur pathar, Palshi, Alkuti, siddheshwarwadi villages are with various angle attraction of tourists.

Conclusion:

Tourism in the tehsil can be well developed in Parner tehsil with proper planning. The development of tourism center are provide employment to thousands of local people. Tourist affects potholes at Nighoj so it needs to be cherished as it is a specific phenomenon. Government will take action and control on construction in Nighoj pothole area. In Parner tehsil huge scope to obtain wind energy in hilly ranges area which will uplift the economic status of the people. At Nighoj pothole and Padali darya cave affected by human traditions.

To the visit of tourist at tourist center which requires natural re-sources, infrastructural and transportation facilities, accommodation, recreation, sightseeing, shopping and variety of facilities and services for use and enjoyments. The success of tourism de-pends on all these facilities. The tourism activity generates employment opportunities in various part of study region.

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